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Introduction to Information Society¹

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Introduction

Today's economy changing its shape and stepping further outside the area of classical mechanisms into sphere of new resources and new economical possibilities. This new economy besides the ordinary market influences: a play of demand and supply is being steered by knowledge and information.

Together with economical changes new type of society is evolving, the Information Society (IS). This society behave and react on the economical stimulation in the new way -demanding production of goods and services of a new kind and quality. IS is basing on a information and communication technology (ICT), which guarantee faster and more efficient access to the resource of the information.

Information Society paradigm is strictly connected with the new economy paradigm. The defining characteristics for a new economy are a focus on increasing globalization and expanding information and communication technology (ICT) as the underlying causes of an evolving economy.

For the purpose of this study the look on IT and ICT is simplified. The equation mark is put between these two terms, because more often IT technology (computers, laptop or desktop, without reference to their connectivity to the internet or lack of it), are naturally used and produced for the purpose of operating in the Internet or other networks. In the literature, ICT has broader meaning. It also include media such as radio, video and telephony, information technology which is used to operate within various telematic networks for transferring and processing information. In further work the ICT term is used as the meaning of IT and ICT.

What makes the information in the new economy unique is that, together with capital, labour and raw materials, is becoming a new, fourth resource.

Information Society can be characterized by the following traits:

- Technology: Sophisticated ICT for the production, recording, transmission and retrieval of information of all formats, bringing about high levels of connectivity, globalization and dependence on ICT.
- Production: Extensive production of information, coupled with a high proportion of the labour force employed directly or indirectly in information activities.
- Economy: Information being a major commodity, bought and sold extensively.

- Operation: Specialized channels and appliances for the handling of specific forms of electronic information may be replaced by integrated channels and appliances.
- Culture: The economic and social accent on information have turned it into a culture, typified by an amplified socio-political role of the media, shrinking time and space constraints, and an emergence of global virtual symbolism and realities.

For the purpose of this study and analytical look, author resigned from sociological and psychological aspects of information society paradigm, paying attention to technological, productive, operational and economical aspect of this problem.

The Information Society and its linkage with the ICT, is nowadays of the highest importance. This problem touches deeply the economical sphere of all countries wanting to play an important role in today's global market. Information Society benefits were first noticed after the successes of the United States in the ICT industrial policy. Theory of economy suggests that ICT is an important factor of the economical stabilization prosperity and healthy economical development.

Electronic commerce, as a part of Information Society services, maintained by small and medium enterprises as well as huge multinational firms, is bringing them to the possibility of the cost control and cost savings, of the deeper market penetration, provision of the economical assistance in a micro and macro scale. For companies, properly applied e-commerce is giving a better chance to succeed.

This study is a result of the author's interest in the information economy – the new economy and Information Society problems. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the evolution and trends in the Information Society as an economical phenomena.

This study concentrates on theoretical aspects of the Information Society –its background, definitions, characteristics and evolution. For the purpose of this study it is important to define the Information Society in less humanistic aspects, underline its common sense with the Global Information Infrastructure and particularly with ICT.

Author is aware of impossibility to exhaust the subject and some important problems have been omitted on purpose or showed in simplified, shortened way.

Believing that the future will be strictly connected with ICT and its use in every aspect of life, author hopes that this study will help to explain correlations between the new economy and Information Society paradigm, which may soon be an overwhelming fact.

Introduction to Information Society

During the last two decades we have observed an enormous dynamics in a technology and information progress. The question arises: In what way does it change the world we live in. It is often claimed that our society is “Information Society”. If it is so, what exactly does it mean and what consequences, opportunities and threats does it creates for the 21st century man.

1.1. Theoretical aspects of Information Society, background

It is generally accepted that for some time now the world has been undergoing a dramatic **information and communication revolution**. Central to this process has been the emergence of new information and communication technologies Information Communication Technologies (ICTs). When we think of the communication revolution, we automatically think of rapid technological developments that are resulting in a convergence of electronic media such as TV, radio, telephones and computer networks. These developments are in turn contributing to a world-wide increase in interactive electronic information and communication applications in practically every walk of life. Manuel Castells, in his trilogy on “The Information age: Economy, Society and Culture”², describes the same process from a slightly broader perspective by stating that the world is undergoing a historic period of transformation to a **new global social order**. In this new order, networking is the major pattern of social organisation. The economy of this new societal system is increasingly characterised by *informationalism* (productivity and success depends on the ability to handle information) and *globalism* (organised on a global scale through networks). The principal driving force of this process has been the development and rapid spread of information and communication technologies, which provide the necessary platform for an emerging “information” economy. It is therefore evident that there are global forces at work that are resulting in an emerging global “informationised” society - also called the **"information society"**.³ In the United States of America this process is often referred to in term of its underlying and enabling technological infrastructure, called the "Information Super

² Manuel Castells, The Information age: Economy, Society and Culture, Vol. 1,2,3,; The Network Society, Oxford: Blackwell, 1996,97,98

³ Information Society Directorate-General Website, http://europa.eu.int/comm/dgs/information_society/index_en.htm, 2002-05-10

Highway".⁴

We all can agree that new technologies such as IT (information technologies) and ICT (information communication technologies) are strongly influencing almost every aspect of our life. The implications of it can be even stronger seen in the sphere of economy, organization, management and related sciences. This fact can not be omitted by the economists, governments and international organisations.

Information society technologies increasingly pervade all industrial and societal activities and are accelerating the globalisation of economies, in particular by providing Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) with new ways to access to the global marketplace, and societies,⁵ says European Communities Council decision.

Many countries are beginning to be aware of changing economical reality, determined by new technologies. They are trying to implement their politics, according to The Information Society Paradigm: based on access to international databases and development of telecommunication infrastructure. The example of such policy can be the state of Polish Government in the field of Aims and directions of the Information Society development in Poland, which explains the background of the problem:

“The progressing emergence of the information civilization is inevitable on the global scale and to downplay it would be short-sighted. Current trends in the world economy demonstrate that ‘general access to information constitutes a precondition of economic development’. It is one of the obligations of the state, enshrined in the Constitution, to ensure such access.”⁶

The importance of Information Society phenomena is again stressed by the European Union in the long policy action plan:

“The accelerated use of information and communication technologies and the advent of the Internet has put very powerful tools within the reach of citizens, governments as well as large and small businesses everywhere. This is resulting in profound changes in the internal organisations of governments and business as well as in the relationships amongst businesses, trading partners, citizens and governments. We now know that these technologies are considered to have a considerable impact on the whole of the economy and that policies

⁴ D.P Conradie, Research issues in the Information Society, SAICSIT (South African Institute for Computer Scientists and Information Technologists) conference held in Pretoria on 28th September 2001), http://osprey.unisa.ac.za/saicsit2001/Electronic/Conradie_Postgrad_Saicsit.pdf, 2002-01-11

⁵ Council Decision of 25 January 1999 adopting a specific program for research, technological development and demonstration on a user-friendly information society (1998 to 2002), Official Journal of the European Communities, 1999-03-12

⁶ Polish State Committee for Scientific Research, Polish Ministry of Posts and Telecommunications, Aims and directions of the information society development in Poland, Warsaw, 28th November 2000, http://www.kbn.gov.pl/en/cele_en.html, 2002-05-10

which govern their use and implementation are decisive in the modernisation of these economies”.⁷

The power of new technologies in economy (often seen as the new economy) is said to be the biggest opportunity for MSEs , which can be undoubtedly the core development of strong an healthy economies.

Use of mobile communications and the internet are increasing at an exponential rate. Convergence of information, communication and content is opening a range of opportunities for new digital businesses to take off. Companies in all sectors have started to restructure to become e-businesses. Small innovative start-ups are finding new markets in internet-based services and content; and some of these may be the industry giants of tomorrow. Schools, hospitals and other public services are embracing new ways of operating. And citizens are discovering new ways to work, shop and communicate.⁸

The impact of the Information Society on people’s life will be important but not clear yet. Less educated part of the population is already affected by the transformation of the western countries. The required skills are much higher in the Information Society and therefore more people might be unable to get the necessary knowledge. For these people another major change is the rapid disappearance of manufacturing jobs from big industrial companies. The globalisation of the economy makes mass production impossible in these countries for reasons of cost-effectiveness. The profit logic induces to produce in countries where wages are incomparably lower (as is their welfare system). In addition, the passage from an industrial to an information society resulted in the shut down of some of these companies. People who occupied these semi-skilled jobs had a chance to have a decent life and therefore avoid exclusion from the job market. Their disappearances weaken their situation even more because they can no longer rely on that kind of jobs and an equivalent does not exist in the Information Society.⁹

The meaning of the Information Society development policy is great. The potential power of cost savings and economical growth mechanism are very important for all modern economies, seen as a particular beings or as a one global economy.

⁷ Candidate Countries with the support of the European Commission, eEurope+, A co-operative effort to implement the Information Society in Europe Action Plan, Göteborg European Summit, 15-16 June 2001, http://europa.eu.int/information_society/international/regulatory/eeuropeplus/doc/eEurope_june2001.pdf

⁸ European Commission Directorate-General Information Society, IST 2000, Realising an Information Society for All, Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2000

⁹ Norbert Guillotin, Living in an e-World, an Information society for all?, http://perso.worldonline.fr/gguillotin/digital_divide_and_information_society.htm, 2002-05-10

1.2. Origins and Definitions of the Information Society concept

The definition of "Information Society" is very difficult to summarise. The development of computer sciences, computerization and informatization processes caused great interest from the side of theorists. In effect such expressions as: information revolution, information age, l'informatization/computerization de société, information- oriented society or "cybersociety", have a similar meaning.

As a concept, information society is neither explicit nor well established. Most of its users agree that the term refers to a new stage of development. The emerging new society has been described in terms as follows:

- expert society (a growing emphasis on expertise)
- information society (information becomes the dominant factor of production)
- post-industrial society (a changing paradigm of production)
- communication society (people linked together by communication technology)
- learning society (the ability to learn will be of critical importance)
- service society (emphasis on services rather than manufacturing)
- post-modern society (modernisation leading to a pluralization and an individualisation of values)¹⁰

The term "information society" has been increasingly in use since the early 1980s, though earlier terms such as the 'age of information' date back to the early 1970s. These and other terms have emerged in the context of attempts to coin societal transformations since the early 1950s. Beniger counted 75 such terms proposed between 1950 and 1984, almost all of which have not been adopted for the naming of our current age. Definitions for the information society highlight two of its major facets, namely the economic and the cultural.

At the economic end, the European Commission has said that 'in an information society, information is the most important commodity', and that culturally it is 'a society that brings about a general flourishing state of human intellectual creativity, instead of affluent material consumption'. Castells related these two facets by claiming that the information society 'is based on the historical tension between the material power of abstract information processing and society's search for meaningful cultural identity'.

The information society consists of two major processes: production and consumption. These do not have to develop to high levels in all aspects. At the production end, several

¹⁰ The Information Society Strategy for Western Finland Alliance, WFA publication, Tampere 1998
<http://www.dmi.tut.fi/paraddis/homepage.htm>, 2002-05-10

things may be produced. One major production process may be the innovation and wide-scale production of the hardware of information society, such as computers and telecommunications devices and equipment. Another major production process may be computer software, and a third one may be information itself, notably electronic, such as Internet sites, television programmes and movies. High levels of consumption of information may too be expressed in both hardware, software and information *per se*. The wide adoption of telecommunications and information devices such as PCs, telephones and TVs is one indicator. Sales of software are another, as are the number and duration of domestic and international phone calls, or the proportion of homes connected to cable TV.¹¹

The first definition of "Information Society" entered public consciousness in the early 1970's with professor Yonedi Masuda's target programme for the future of Japan. According to Masuka's programme, Japan should aim at a "johoka shakai" (an information society) by developing computer and communication technology. In his principal work *Information Society as a Post Industrial Society* (1980), Masuka classifies societies in three categories: the pre- industrial, the industrial and the post-industrial. There is a great interest in the information society in all industrialised countries. The European Union has addressed the subject in Bangemann's report *Europe and the Global Information Society* (1994) and in the expert group report *Building the European Information Society for Us All* (1996). Other initiatives include the extensive United States government programme called *The National Information Infrastructure* (1993) and the Japanese programme *The Intellectually Creative Society Based on Info- Communications* (1993) that focuses on telecommunication.¹²

Increasingly, information is regarded as a defining feature of the modern world, and it is commonplace to refer to countries such as the United States and Britain as "information societies". Commentators are, however, strikingly vague about the criteria used to define either information or information societies. Five analytical criteria, i.e.:

- technological,
- economic,
- occupational,
- spatial,
- cultural,

¹¹ Aharon Kellerman, Phases in the rise of Information Society, Info Vol 2, No 6 Camford Publishing Ltd, December 2000

¹² Norbert Guillotin, Living in an e-World, an Information society for all?, http://perso.worldonline.fr/gguillot/digital_divide_and_information_society.htm, 2001-11-10

are used to define either information or information societies.

Most definitions are concerned with quantitative measures, which fail to consider important qualitative dimensions of the criteria, though ironically, there is the widespread presumption that quantitative changes in information herald a new type of society, one qualitatively different from predecessors. Further, proponents of an information society operate with non-semantic conceptions of information. Against this, when information is approached in common sense terms, that is, in terms of its meanings, then the prospects for an approaching information society are unconvincing.¹³

A definition of the Information Society should differentiate description, what the IS is, regardless of what we think of it, from prescription - what the IS should be, what values the IS we want to build should incorporate.

In a first place a descriptive definition should be established:

The Information Society is a society where the ability to access, search, use, create and exchange information is the key for individual and collective well-being.

The Information Society is a society which effectively utilizes information/knowledge and their related technologies to expedite the process of human, social and economic development. Its progress relies on the efficient use and exchange of information. It aims at building a digital nervous system that provides unlimited knowledge management resources for further progress and knowledge creation.

The second meaning of IS is describing Information Society as a common infrastructure:

It is a society where information and knowledge, as well as the related technologies, play a key role in production, education, social relationships, politics...

The roots for the “Industrial Society” were primarily (although not only) economic: It arose from a fundamental change in the structure of production and commerce. The same goes for the “Information Society”. The **Information Economy** is an economy where information and knowledge become primary production factors and, through a sharp reduction in their own cost of production and circulation, contribute to more global and frictionless markets. It is also an economy where the importance of information and knowledge-based economic sectors and products becomes dominant.

This “infrastructure” is fundamentally global. However, many different societies can become information societies, while remaining very different. Historical, cultural, religious,

¹³ Frank Webster, “What Information Society?”, The Information Society Volume 10 Number 1, 1994, <http://bubl.ac.uk/journals/lis/fj/infosoc/v10n0194.htm>, 2002-05-10

linguistic, political differences will remain within the framework of the information society. There can be democratic and non-democratic information societies, religious and non-religious information societies, developed and developing information societies, capitalist and socialist information societies.

In conclusion, the Information Society is a society which effectively utilizes information/knowledge and their related technologies to promote human well-being.¹⁴

The concept of global information society is often treated as synonymous merely with the growth of information and communication technology (ICT). However, it has in fact a much broader meaning, for what becomes decisive for the development of the information society is the fact that "information becomes a prime production resource (next to raw materials, capital and labour) and the use of the information technology in this process is merely a matter of instrumentation". This is precisely the difference between the:

- *global information society*, interpreted in civilisational and humanistic terms and promoted in the European Union, and the
- *global information technology infrastructure*, which is promoted in the United States.

These differences notwithstanding, the foundations for the growth of the *information society* are undoubtedly constituted by the *knowledge-based economy*, and "knowledge resources, i.e. information and way of using it, become the crucial economic resource, which is accumulated both in databases and in the intellectual potential of the society".¹⁵

¹⁴ Daniel Kaplan, U.N. World Summit on the Information Society / Copet Initial Preparatory Workshop / 2001, Dec. 5-6, http://newuses.net/doc/kaplan_IS%definition.doc, 2002-05-10

¹⁵ Council Decision of 25 January 1999 adopting a specific program for research, technological development and demonstration on a user-friendly information society (1998 to 2002), Official Journal of the European Communities, 1999-12-03

1.2.1. Global Information Society - European Union definition.

In the context of EU regional policy, Information Society refers to the socio-economic impact of the rapid diffusion of Information and Communication-related Technologies (ICT) throughout the economy and society.¹⁶

The concept of “Information Society” was launched by the Commission’s White Paper on Growth, Competitiveness and Employment (1993). This term was chosen deliberately in preference to “information highways”, which stresses infrastructure aspects; it alludes not only to the networks, services and content conveyed, but also to the social, societal and cultural transformations brought about by the development and dissemination of information and communication technologies (ICT).

This choice of term was no accident. It is indicative of a change in public policy-making with respect to ICT. Because of their anticipated impact on the economy, employment and quality of life (new services), ICT - which were previously viewed in sectoral terms (telecommunications, research and development) - are now identified as an overall political priority of the EU and its Member States, incorporating the various aspects covered by this new concept.

The term Information Society describes a normative moral and social vision, based on "flow" (of information), interactive flow, as central moral value. It claims that: it is a primary moral duty of humans to exchange information, that it is a primary goal of the state to facilitate this, that culture should value flow of information, and that an infrastructure for information flow should be provided, if necessary by the state.

In this definition, pre-modern or pre-industrial societies can also be information societies. Historically, however, such societies follow on the European liberal tradition, and the "Information Society" concept is a part of that tradition. It is not a neutral sociological term..¹⁷

Contemporary information society can be characterized by the following traits:

- Technology: Sophisticated ICT for the production, recording, transmission and retrieval of information of all formats, bringing about high levels of connectivity, globalization and dependence on ICT.
- Production: Extensive production of information, coupled with a high proportion of the labour force employed directly or indirectly in information activities.

¹⁶ North East of England Objective 2, Programme 2000 –2006, Information Society Guidance Note, ICT Guidance, 2001 April

¹⁷ Information Society: Definition: <http://web.inter.nl.net/users/Paul.Treanor/is.def.html> 2000-10-11

- Economy: Information being a major commodity, bought and sold extensively.
- Operation: Specialized channels and appliances for the handling of specific forms of electronic information may be replaced by integrated channels and appliances.
- Culture: The economic and social accent on information have turned it into a culture, typified by an amplified socio-political role of the media, shrinking time and space constraints, and an emergence of global virtual symbolism and realities.¹⁸

1.2.2. Global Information Technology Infrastructure.

This approach to Information Society paradigm is strongly connected with its technical aspect. In that case the technological and operational aspect of the Information Society is stressed and this approach is mainly considered by the United States policy.

The concept of global information infrastructures-global information society (GII-GIS) encompasses the development and integration of high speed communication networks, and a set of core services and applications in digital format, into global integrated networks capable of seamless delivery. Such networks provide fully interactive access, to network-based services within countries and across national borders. These services may be traditional voice services, data, video services, or more sophisticated combinations of these services (multimedia services) destined for business, government and residential users, as well as for social purposes. The physical infrastructure of GII-GIS is not limited to any one technology; on the contrary implicit in the GII-GIS concept is the interconnection and interoperability of a range of competing and complementary infrastructures, applications and services made possible by digitalisation. Communication and computing technologies form the basis of GII-GIS, but hardware, software, multimedia skills, content and information also play a key role. A harbinger of GII-GIS is the explosive growth of the Internet.

The concept of GII-GIS also encompasses the notion of the transformation of existing economic markets to a market place where communication networks bundling together transport, access and market transactions will play a major role. The driving forces behind economic growth and development in such a networked economy will not be natural resources or physical goods but based on information viewed as providing the foundation for the transformation of existing social and economic relationships.¹⁹

The Clinton Administration has made the development of an advanced National

¹⁸ European Commission Directorate-General Information Society, IST 2000, Realising an Information Society for All, Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2000

¹⁹ Committee for Information, Computers and Communication Policy, Global Information Infrastructure –Global Information Society Policy Requirements, OECD 1997

Information Infrastructure (NII) and the GII top U.S. priorities. A major goal of the NII is to give our citizens access to a broad range of information and information services. Using innovative telecommunications and information technologies, the NII - through a partnership of business, labour, academia, consumers, and all levels of government - will help the United States achieve a broad range of economic and social goals.

The GII will depend upon an ever-expanding range of technology and products, including telephones, fax machines, computers, switches, compact discs, video and audio tape, coaxial cable, wire, satellites, optical fiber transmission lines, microwave networks, televisions, scanners, cameras, and printers, as well as advances in computing, information, and networking technologies not yet envisioned.

But the GII extends beyond hardware and software; it is also a system of applications, activities, and relationships. There is the information itself, whatever its purpose or form, e.g., video programming, scientific or business databases, images, sound recordings, library archives, or other media. There are also standards, interfaces, and transmission codes that facilitate interoperability between networks and ensure the privacy and security of the information carried over them, as well as the security and reliability of the networks themselves. Most importantly, the GII includes the people involved in the creation and use of information, development of applications and services, construction of the facilities, and training necessary to realize the potential of the GII. These individuals are primarily in the private sector, and include vendors, operators, service providers, and users.²⁰

1.3. Characteristics of Information Society

Around various definitions of the Information Society paradigm there exist some common factors of its characteristics. Out of the most important we can distinguish:

- the development of **information as a central strategic resource** in industrial and economic development (hence the centrality of Drucker's 'knowledge workers') on the management and application of which individual units (companies, nations, geographical regions) are increasingly dependent for their competitiveness; of course, all technological

²⁰ Ronald H. Brown, The Global Information Infrastructure: Agenda for Cooperation, Secretary of Commerce Chair, Information Infrastructure Task Force, <http://iitf.doc.gov/documents/docs/gii/giiagend.html>, 2002-05-10

changes have always been dependent on information, but 'what differentiates the current process of technological change is that *its raw material itself is information, and so is its outcome*²¹ or, again, 'what is specific to the informational mode of development is the action of knowledge upon knowledge itself as the main source of productivity'²²

- the very rapid growth in **informatization of the economy** which allows closer links between regional, national and international economies, as well as breaking down the conventional barriers between financial sectors as all work, including manufacturing, becomes increasingly a matter of the transmission of information
- the development of **global information networks** on which what Castells refers to as the 'network society' is based and without which the rapid rise of trans-national corporations (TNCs) would have been impossible; there are now only around a couple of dozen national economies bigger than the economies of the major TNCs
- the **globalisation of capitalism** which is facilitated by and is dependent upon those networks, permitting economic decision-making on a world scale in real time; the term globalisation does not refer simply to improved ease of communication and interaction between nation states, nor is it purely limited to the economic and business spheres; certainly, globalisation does refer to such developments, but refers also to significant cultural changes, including for example greater migration, more international tourism, the development of 'world music', greater international co-operation in political, economic and ecological matters; a minor, but none the less telling, example of this cultural change can be found in the international advertising of certain consumer goods such as jeans, where advertisers often no longer see any necessity to provide different ads for different national markets; it is important, too, to consider the detachment from local constraints, which is afforded by internationalisation of the economy, leading to 'a trend that we would call "bureaucratization" in the Weberian sense, that is the predominance of the rationality of means over the rationality of goals the interests of a local business élite, or of a local resident working class, or of a local market, will be constantly subordinated to the need for the organization to be connected simultaneously with the financial markets, the pool of professional labour, the necessary technology'
- the **reduction in the constraints of space**, whereby Silicon Valley, for example, becomes just another node in the network society, its actual geographical location being largely

²¹ Manuel Castells, *The Informational City - Information Technology, Economic Restructuring and the Urban-regional Process* Oxford: Blackwell, 1989

²² Manuel Castells, *The Information age: Economy, Society and Culture*, Vol. 1,2,3,; *The Network Society*, Oxford: Blackwell, 1996,97,98

irrelevant in an economy which has passed, in Negroponte's terms, from shifting around atoms to shifting around bits.²³

From all the features of Information Society, the globalisation seems to be one of the most characteristic.

There is no widely agreed upon definition of “globalisation”, nor a unified body of theory on this phenomenon. The definition of globalisation as the intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations is a good base for trying to explain it. First, this process is an economic one. Economy has now a global aspect, everything seems linked, and for example, the last Asian economic crisis had an effect on all markets. The influence of trans-national companies is increasing with consequently the homogenisation of markets, which is damaging for cultural diversity. In addition, for some writers globalisation is primarily the extension and triumph of the capitalism ideas over the world’s economy and political systems, especially since the collapse of the Soviet Union. Even if there are some debates on what exactly globalisation is, there is widespread agreement on its effects. In a world in which time and space have become compressed because of the operation of modern transport, communications and the increasing internationalisation of economic activity. Thus actions in one part of the globe have consequences elsewhere.

Since all events are interlinked, one needs a powerful communication tool in order to know quickly what is going on. That is where the development of information technology combined with the globalisation process gives us the possibility to access information and to transmit it quasi-instantly. For Castells we can speak of an Information Society and in the same way sociologists have been referring to the existence of an industrial society, characterized by common fundamental features in their socio-technical systems. He also explains that the importance of digital technology is captured by the term "Information society" often used instead of post- industrial society.²⁴

For others socio-economists, the technological revolution which is producing this connectivity will change globalisation in dramatic and still unanticipated ways. According to this, the combination of globalisation and the new technologies affects not only on the economy but also the whole society’s social structures. Some authors go even further, arguing

²³ Mick Underwood, Information Society, <http://www.cultsock.ndirect.co.uk/MUHome/cshtml/media/infotech.html>, 2001-11-10

²⁴ Manuel Castells, The rise of the network society, Blackwell Publishers, 1996

that The Internet is also changing, the self perception of what it means to be a human being today and will bring along new ethical challenges to the Information society.²⁵

1.4. Background history of the Information Society

The developed industrial societies reached its peak in the early 1970's. The maturing of these economies meant that industrial processes had reached a certain level of automation in the production processes and also in the control of those processes. These industries had been the core of industrial society, like manufacturing industries. The essential nature of these industries was labour intensity in the beginning, and mass production. Now, this labour intensity decreased due to the automation, as technology replaced labour.

Also, the industrial or modern society has been described as mass society. The mass production was meant for rather homogenous markets. The modern industrial countries emphasized the role of the state, in many of the modern societies, excluding the U.S. where the corporate strategy was the main power in society.

The first phase of information society took place in the late 1970's and during 1980's. This was post-industrial society era when service industries grew, and there was a market for new industries in industrial societies. The typical characteristics of these industries, information industries, is that they are technologically developed high-tech industries, they involve high-level of Research and Development input, and they are sold in mass markets.

The modern society reached a turning point in the 1970's, when industrial state had reached a certain saturation point. There are at least two schools of thought in the analysis of post-industrial society. One looks at the post-industrial society as a continuation of an industrial society, the other as a new form of society. This latter school of thought has further been divided into :

- analysis of post-modernity which looks at the society after the modern as a completely different kind of society and
- information oriented society which finds information important in the development of society and economy.

²⁵ Norbert Guillotin, Living in an e-World, an Information society for all?, http://perso.worldonline.fr/gguillot/digital_divide_and_information_society.htm, 2002-05-10

Post-modernity looks at the development of a society as something passed the modernity. It rejects the modern society, and emphasizes new ways of thinking and categories and genres. The Post-modernity also looks at the culture and the nature of society more than the economy as a leading model of society. The economic growth has been priority, and countries like the U.S., Japan and many European countries have produced programs and strategies to build their economy on the information industries and infrastructure. Telecommunications has become a leading strategy of development in these countries.²⁶

Various authors talk about changes in total production as a syndrome of a emerging Information Society.

Commonly, the supposedly new form of society is referred to as a *post-industrial society* or an *information society*. The claim that we are living in a 'post-industrial society' is associated with Professor Daniel Bell, who cited in favour of his claim figures showing that in 1947 over half the US workforce was employed in goods-producing sectors and just under a half in the service sector. By 1980, he predicted, the share of the workforce employed in the manufacturing sector would fall to 32%. This prediction has certainly been borne out by developments in all developed industrial nations. In Glasgow, for example, one of the new 'post-industrial' cities, employment in the service sector now accounts for 84% of jobs, up from 60% in the eighties. In fact, taken over a longer period, the most striking change in employment patterns has been a shift from the agricultural to the service sector and the decline of employment in the manufacturing sector is a more recent phenomenon. Recent though it may be, that collapse of employment in manufacturing has been remarkably swift and dramatic.

Theorists of the information society often look back to Fritz Machlup's 1962 book *The Production and Distribution of Knowledge in the United States*, in which he claimed that the 'knowledge industry' represented 29% of the US gross national product. Furthermore, as Manuel Castells points out, the notion of post-industrial society is a purely negative one, referring to the fact that manufacturing is no longer at the centre of the economy, in itself a questionable claim. Castells points out that the rise in importance of services cannot be directly correlated with the decline of manufacturing, since the rise in service jobs has been as the result of transfers from the agricultural sector, as well as of the entry into the labour market of new kinds of workers, especially women, who filled 85% of the new service jobs created between 1975 and 1985. In fact, Castells argues that the division of the economy into

²⁶ Helena Tapper, Understanding of Information Society Paradigm, 14-09-1998 , <http://www.helsinki.fi/~naalisva/argonaut/paradigm.html>, 2001-11-08

primary, secondary and tertiary sectors is simplistic and misleading, the so-called 'service sector' being composed of such a wide diversity of types of jobs that it is meaningless to lump them all together into a single 'sector'. A substantial part of employment in services, particularly in social services and personal services, is in fact a way of absorbing the surplus population generated by increased productivity in agriculture and industry, in a society that still requires salaried work to survive, even if we could achieve greater collective output with less collective work.

Nevertheless, popular gurus like Alvin Toffler cite Machlup as the prophet of what Toffler refers to as the 'third wave', the first two being the invention of agriculture and industry. Similarly Peter Drucker, who, long before computers arrived on every desktop, predicted that the major changes in society would be brought about by information, argues that knowledge has become the central, key resource that knows no geography. It underlies the most significant and unprecedented social phenomenon of this century. No class in history has ever risen as fast as the blue-collar worker and no class has ever fallen as fast. All within less than a century.

Drucker points to the rapid decline in the steel-manufacturing workforce in the US, from 120,000 people in 1980 to a mere 20,000 now, producing the same tonnage. Agricultural workers have dwindled to a negligible number in most developed countries and blue collar workers, who actually represented the majority of all workers in 1950s Britain, were predicted by Drucker to fall to one eighth by the year 2000. According to Drucker, the largest single group will become what he refers to as *knowledge workers*, whose defining characteristic is the level of their formal education. Thus formal education, though not necessarily carried out in schools, will become the central concern in *knowledge societies*.²⁷

1.5. Processes leading to the Information Society

Whether industrial society has given way to information society by continuity or change has been extensively debated. On the one hand, the development of information and communication technology (ICT) and the need for skilled workers who consume and produce more information are viewed as nesting within industrial society, and the subsequent service economy. On the other hand, Castells argues that information technologies allow 'a direct, on-line linkage between different types of activity in the same process of production,

²⁷ Mick Underwood, Information Society, <http://www.cultsock.ndirect.co.uk/MUHome/cshtml/media/infotech.html>, 2001-11-10

management and distribution, establishing a close, structural connection between spheres of work and employment [that were once] artificially separated by obsolete statistical categories'. Thus, at a certain stage information and knowledge may replace labour and possibly also capital as leading production factors. Capitalism has been recognized as a major force in the emergence of an information society by facilitating the transfer of information from the public to the private sector, or 'the privatization of information'. This process involved the rise of a class of technocrats in the so-called 'programmed society', in conflict with more disparate groups being governed or managed by them.

A third major force in the rise of information technology and society in the USA was the Cold War. Computers were widely required for missiles and defense from missiles, as well as for space exploration. Furthermore, the modern Internet had its roots in the Pentagon's ARPANET system. A fourth major dimension facilitating the emergence of the information society is the nature of cultural activity in developed societies, which by the 1960s required a constant and rich transmission of written and oral information. The accent on information was not novel but before it had been constrained by volume, form, time and distance.

1.5.1. Information-rich society (1960s–1970s)

With these four dimensions in place, the first phase in the evolution of the information society took place in the 1960s–1970s, and may be termed 'information-rich' society. The characteristics of this phase included growing emphases on information production and use through the development of IT. Growing employment in information-related activities has been recognized as an early and central aspect of information societies. Katz writes: 'The term 'information society' has been used to describe socioeconomic systems that exhibit high employment of information-related occupations and wide diffusion of information technologies'. Porat and Machlup showed that a large proportion of US workers were already 'information workers' by the 1960s, employed in information-related occupations (the so called 'knowledge sector'), followed in the 1970s–1980s by other leading economies. However, it was not until a later phase in the emergence of the information society that information became a common thread in production as well as consumption, through the introduction of personal computing and a common channel of information flow, the Internet.

Figure 1: Phases in the rise of information society.

Source : Aharon Kellerman, Phases in the rise of Information Society, Info Vol. 2, No 6, Camford Publishing, Ltd December 2000

The introduction of ICT via computers and telecommunications, and its rapid and wide diffusion and adoption, have become the driving forces of information society. The impact of ICT over the years has been on two levels. On the one hand it has been a major enabling force for society, allowing inexpensive data recording and storage, and fast processing and transmission of information. But it has also become an extensive industry in itself, the high-tech industry, characterized by intensive R&D (Research and Development) and entrepreneurship. A third major aspect of the information rich society of the 1960s–1970s was the growth in information production. It seems obvious that the introduction of ICT and the growth in information use would lead to larger volumes of information. However, this growth had also to do with the expansion of research and study in universities and research institutes during these decades, yielding ever increasing numbers of books and journals.

1.5.2. Information-based society (1980s–1990s)

The growth in information volume, technology and employment led to a second phase in the emergence of information society, the information-based society of the 1980s–1990s. This phase has been characterized by three trends, all based, in their part, on developments in the first phase.

1. Globalization

The ability to move information instantaneously worldwide has become possible with the rapid development of international telephony, the Internet and cable/satellite television. These technological breakthroughs have reduced or completely removed international boundaries to the movement of information. This has been evident in almost every economic, social and cultural area, including news coverage, banking, commerce and social contact. The pace of information production and interaction has quickened as space has evaporated.

2. Specialization

The second phase in the rise of the information society has also been typified by the rapid diffusion and adoption of ‘information devices’ such as telephones, cellular telephones, fax machines, personal computers, television sets and the like. Special appliances have evolved for specific uses of information, together with specialist suppliers of equipment, software and information.

3. Connectivity

A third characteristic of information-based society has been increased connectivity. Internet technologies have permitted the recording and transmission of all forms of information including text, data, graphics, voice and pictures in electronic digital bit format. Coupled with fast and low-priced telecommunications and PCs they have allowed increased connectedness of individual customers with goods producers and service providers, as well as among service providers themselves. Furthermore, the interrelationship between electronic information and printed information has changed with the introduction of low-priced high quality laser printers and optical scanners, permitting non-professional users to produce high quality paper information products. These developments have rendered society in developed countries increasingly information-dependent.

1.5.3. Information-dominated society (1990s–2000s)

Unfolding in the late 1990s towards the 2000s is a third phase in the rise of the information society which might be termed information dominated society. Information production,

transmission and use, becomes a leading if not the leading economic and social activity, both as a product in itself and as a service leading to the production or consumption of material products. As such, three additional characteristics are added to information society:

- information becoming a major product;
- information media beginning to fuse into each other;
- information becoming a culture.

Information has increasingly become a commodity in its own right. By the late 1990s revenues from the sale of information were matching those from the sale of material products and services. Major examples are the sale of data sets relating to Internet users, or the tremendous growth in the sales of software and TV programmes. The USA has become the world leader in the sale and distribution of electronic information. Liberalization trends in the provision of information services to households, as well as technological advances, have brought about early signs of possible fusions among different forms of information, their transmission and use. Thus it has become possible, for example, to use the computer also as a telephone, fax and TV, and receive several of these services from a single service provider. This fusion may possibly mature into a single appliance for information consumption and production, as well as so-called ‘public networks’ of data and software. The information society becomes at this third phase of its development a society with a culture of information.²⁸

The last phase of Information Dominated Society development is determined not only by societies culture consciousness but also by trends that capture the transformative effects of ICTs in the emergence of the information society. Through the ICT trends we can distinguish:

- The rapid **evolution of the Internet** – the Internet (and the World Wide Web) has become the backbone of the knowledge-based economy and information society and the platform for new applications including hardware, software and services. The *research implications* of this evolution are immense: especially if one thinks of the availability of research related *on-line data*, publications, resources and services.

²⁸ Aharon Kellerman, Phases in the rise of Information Society, Info Vol. 2, No 6, Camford Publishing Ltd, 2000 December

- Growth in **infrastructure and applications** – increased bandwidth and improved connectivity make new and improved applications possible, which in turn stimulates the need for more bandwidth and better connectivity, as well as content. The *research implications* are obvious - new applications need research to be *developed*, and once implemented, research is again needed for *impact assessment* and *optimising*.
- **Globalisation** and deregulation have transformed the workforce. Business investment has shifted from bricks and mortar to ICT applications and infrastructure. As global information society forces have made themselves felt in societies, this has raised new research issues (such as the impact of the Internet on national *identity*, or *cultural imperialism*)
- The **evolution of business models** in the private and public sectors – the emergence of the digital economy and the e-business revolution are redefining business models, particularly with lesser emphasis on physical capital and more emphasis on human capital focused on customers and leveraged more effectively to drive growth. This poses the *research problem* of how to understand the *dynamics* of these new processes.
- The **linkage of ICT and social infrastructure** – the ICT revolution has changed the nature and level of interaction between citizens and community development organisations, public institutions and government.²⁹

²⁹ D.P Conradie, Research issues in the Information Society, South African Institute for Computer Scientists and Information Technologists (SAICSIT), conference paper, Pretoria, 28th September 2001, http://osprey.unisa.ac.za/saicsit2001/Electronic/Conradie_Postgrad_Saicsit.pdf, 2002-01-11

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